

The Relationship among Customer Satisfaction, Employee Satisfaction and Business Performance: A Study in Libya Hotels

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Abstract

This article has been prepared to demonstrate the relationship between employee satisfaction, employee performance and business performance in Libyan hotels, the role of customer satisfaction to improve performance. The aim of this study; to determine the relationship between employee satisfaction, business performance and customer satisfaction in Libyan hotels. In addition, as a result of this study, the role of customer satisfaction in increasing business performance will be determined. Four and five stars hotels in Libya were analyzed, and data were collected with face-to-face survey method with these hotels. In order to reveal the relationship between study variables, the survey data were subjected to factor analysis, and the Social Sciences Statistics Package (SPSS) was used to determine the relationship between correlation analysis and variables. There is a statistically significant relationship between the study variables to improve customer satisfaction. As a result of the study, it was determined that there is a statistically significant relationship between the study variables, which will be determinant in increasing customer satisfaction. From this study, it is concluded that the hotel industry in Libya needs to identify the main factors that cause employee well-being. Hotels should improve their practices on the well-being of employees in order to enhance their sense of belonging and strengthen their loyalty. Because there is a positive relationship between motivating employees and providing employee satisfaction and customer satisfaction.

Keywords: Satisfaction, employee satisfaction, customer satisfaction, performance, business performance, the hotel industry, JEL Classification: M11

1. Introduction

Through several studies, there is a positive relationship among employee satisfaction, customer satisfaction, and business performance; according to (Chi and

Gursoy 2009) remarked that employee satisfaction is thought used to express employee satisfaction with the work environment, his treatment, social relations, income, social rights, and others. And how satisfied are they with their jobs?

According to (Küçük 2020), noted that expectations and perceptions include customer satisfaction. Satisfaction is the case if the perceived quality of a product or service meets expectations.

Xu and Geodegebuure (2005) commented that employee satisfaction and customer satisfaction are positively correlated. The Customer Satisfaction Scale, which can be used in scientific research, was developed by (Küçük 2020), which evaluated to give more accurate measurement results. Its validity and reliability have found in this field. Scotti, Driscoll et al. (2007) observed that employee perceptions of customer service are linked to customer perceptions of high-quality.

According to Jung and Yoon (2013) remarked that when you provide employees with the tools and skills they need, employee satisfaction rises, as does service customers' ability. The purpose of this study examined the relationships among employees' satisfaction and business performance to improve customer satisfaction in the Libyan hotels' performance.

2. Review of the Literature

Customer satisfaction has been one of the most frequently discussed topics in the hotel industry literature. Previous studies indicate that employees are more likely to play a significant role in customer service (Wakefield and Blodgett 1999), and hotel employees tend to be more involved in hospitality service offerings. Ahmad, Wasay et al. (2012) say that employee motivation and its four components, e.g. work environment, pay and benefits, management systems, and organizational vision, positively influence customer satisfaction, by researchers (Tsai, Cheng et al. 2010).

Empirical results confirmed that wages and bonuses, in addition to promotion,

have a significant impact on employee satisfaction and business performance. The relationship among the principal drivers of employee satisfaction and customer satisfaction and performance was further examined. According to (Ariani 2015) mentioned that satisfied employees would be associated with better customer service. To perform a better business, hotels have to combine all variables (employee satisfaction, business performance, and customer satisfaction) rather than simply focusing their efforts on marketing strategy only, as ensuring the highest level of customer satisfaction must become the most important (Fatmasari, Al et al. 2018)

Burke, Graham et al. (2005), observe positive and statistically significant relationships between employee satisfaction and customer satisfaction. Satisfaction is primarily influenced by the value of services provided to customers, created by satisfied, loyal, and productive employees, Jung and Yoon (2013).

Several studies support the argument that satisfied employees are more likely to do better hotel services. From an academic perspective, experts in the hotel industry will benefit knowing the relationship between employee satisfaction and business performance in improving customer satisfaction (Jeon and Choi 2012). The expected findings will play a role in filling the gap in customer satisfaction literature. Therefore, this study hypothesized a significant positive relationship between employee satisfaction, business performance to improve customer satisfaction.

This study aims to know the relationship between employee satisfaction, customer satisfaction, and business performance, and its role in improving customer satisfaction in Libyan hotels. For this purpose, hypotheses have been proposed and tested.

According to (Küçük 2020), there is a direct link between employee satisfaction and customer satisfaction. Sageer, Rafat et al. (2012) say that develop strategies to strengthen the work environment and increase employee morale and employee satisfaction to enhance employee performance and productivity to achieve high profits and customer satisfaction and customer retention.

According to Bulgarella (2005), employees could strongly contribute to an organization's success by having a customer-centric approach in their work and their work-related interactions. Employees who are positive about their work become more enthusiastic, energetic, and confident in what they do. According to Bakker, Schaufeli et al. (2008), employees have high positive energy levels identify strongly with their work. When staff mastered what they do, they will provide a quick solution to your customers. The declines number of unhappy customers and increases positive customer feedback. Therefore, the following hypothesis has proposed:

Hypothesis 1: There is a hypothesized significant positive relationship between employee satisfaction and customer satisfaction.

Business Performance Management enables an organization to monitor, control effectively, and manage the implementation of strategic initiatives. business performance management is one of the hottest topics in the hotel industry (Miranda, 2004). Customer satisfaction is an increasingly powerful dimension of business performance (Kristensen, Martensen et al. 2000). According to Williams and Naumann (2011), there are significant and moderate-to-strong associations between satisfaction levels and a firm's financial and market performance.

Singh and Ranchhod (2004), Finding that customer orientation and customer satisfaction orientation have a more substantial impact on performance than the other dimensions(customer orientation, competitor orientation, departmental responsiveness, customer satisfaction orientation), and competitor orientation has a relationship with the account. Jyoti and (2012) showed a significant relationship between business performance, employee satisfaction and customer satisfaction had been explored by many types of research. according to Neupane (2014) say that customer satisfaction has a weak positive relationship with business performance.

According to (Kanten and Darma 2017), customer satisfaction has a positive and significant impact on business performance. Also, t that marketing strategy and customer satisfaction strengthen the effect of consumer behaviour on business performance. the customers and measuring customers' satisfaction are essential in companies' continuous quality improvement, leading to improved business performance, including economic performance. (Kristensen, Martensen et al., 2002). therefore, the following hypothesis has proposed:

Hypothesis 2: There is a hypothesized significant positive relationship between business performance and customer satisfaction.

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Hypothesis 3: There is a hypothesized significant positive relationship between customer satisfaction and business performance.

3. The Research Models

Figure 1 has been showed the research framework.

Figure 1. Model for Employee Satisfaction, Business Performance, and Customer Satisfaction Variables

The model showed that have been researched in study, the relationship among employee satisfaction, business performance, and customer satisfaction.

4. Methodology and Data Collection

Data for this study were obtained from employees and customers of four and five-star hotels in western Libya. This study

uses a quantitative approach. A quantitative approach is an approach that emphasizes testing theories or concepts through the variable metric measurements (Cooke and Rousseau 1988) and performing data analysis procedures with statistical tools and aims to test the hypothesis. They recruited to participate in the study using a random sample in the

hotels. Customer satisfaction data and employee surveys were collected sample randomly through surveys conducted in all targeted Libyan hotels. Employee surveys were used randomly sample assigned to employees who have worked at the hotel for at least eight months. Anonymity has been made for all employees. Employees were directed to fill out surveys and post them on social media.

Eligible employees and clients returned usable questionnaires that yielded 280 valid surveys, 200 customer surveys, and 80 employee surveys. This entire process has been coordinated with Libyan Hotels Human Resources management. Abawi

(2013) declares that the questionnaire is a consistent series of data collection for questions and other claims to gather respondents' information. The questionnaire for measuring employee satisfaction, business performance, and customer satisfaction has been developed (Küçük 2020). These summary scores have been used for employee and customer satisfaction in Libyan hotels because they enable the researcher to reduce the measurement error inherent in the measured variables.

5. Factor Analysis

Table 1. showed that factor analysis for employee satisfaction scale.

Table 1. Factor Analysis For Employee Satisfaction Scale.

Employee Satisfaction	Factor Load	Core value	variance Explanati on Rate (%)	Cronbach Alfa	Average	KMO value
10. Employees who do an excellent job in the company have a chance to be promoted	.839	5.46	54.65	.905	3.04	.860
4. There is enough space for works to be done.	.836				3.13	
5. Employees are provided with training on needed subjects.	.831				2.82	
6. Employees can quickly adapt to new technologies.	.806				2.97	
3. Tools provide ease of use.	.759				2.90	
1.workload is distributed relatively to employee	.687				2.99	
7. There are opportunities for personal and career development.	.686				2.82	
8. There are promotion opportunities in the company.	.651				2.99	
9. The level of wages received for the work done is promising. Salary-Reward-Promotion	.637				2.96	
2. The working conditions are hygienically suitable.	.613				3.02	

The pilot study on hotels, three different questionnaires were used namely, customer satisfaction, employee satisfaction, and the business performance questionnaire used the Table 1. shown that Factor analysis of employee satisfaction by

using analysis of Kaiser-MeyerOlkin (KMO) was found to be 0.860; since this value is over 0.4 or even 0.5, it is confirmed that sampling is sufficient and meaningful factors obtained from research data. All expressions have a factor load

more significant than 0.5, and an eigenvalue greater than 1 indicates that the words are suitable for analysis. Cronbach's alpha coefficient was 0.905. since this value is more significant than 0.80, the

scale is highly reliable, and the variance explanation rate is 54.65%. Thus, it decided that the scale used in scientific research only (Küçük 2016: 227-232).

Table 2. Factor analysis for business performance scale

Business Performance	Factor Load	Core value	Variance Explanation Rate(%)	Cronbach Alfa	Average	KMO value
21.The job satisfaction level of employees of our business is high.	.792	5.86	63.97	.922	2.77	.851
19.The sales volume of our business is higher compared to its competitors.	.767				2.51	
14.The level of benefiting from modern production methods of our company is higher than its competitors.	.753				2.96	
20.Employees of our company receive in-service training, and they are provided continuously to improve themselves.	.750				2.56	
13.-Our company has a high innovation capacity in developing new products compared to its	.739				2.50	
18.. The profitability of our business is high compared to its competitors.	.737				2.65	
16.The customer satisfaction of our business is high compared to its competitors	.729				2.38	
11.The product quality of our business is high compared to its competitors	.724				2.97	
15.The corporate reputation of our company is high compared to its competitors	.715				2.45	
17.Our business has a high market share compared to its competitors.	.666				2.40	
12.The cost of final products of our business is low compared to its competitors	.662				2.66	

As shown in Table .2. Factor analysis for business performance: The value of Kaiser-MeyerOlkin (KMO) found to be 0.851 since this value is over 0.4 or even 0.5. It is proved that sampling is sufficient and meaningful factors obtained from research data. All expressions have a factor load more significant than 0.5, and

an eigenvalue greater than 1 indicates that the terms are suitable for analysis. Cronbach's alpha coefficient was 0.905. since this value is more significant than 0.80, the scale is highly reliable, and the variance explanation rate is 54.65%. Thus, it decided that the scale used in scientific only (Küçük 2016).

Table 3. Factor Analysis For Customer Satisfaction Scale

Customer Satisfaction	Factor Load	Core value	Variance Explanation Rate(%)	Cronbach Alfa	Average	KMO value
33.The products and services offered by the firm are of high quality.	.832	6.78	65.72	.928	2.98	855
34.The error rate in transactions is shallow.	.832				2.98	
28. I find the experience of the staff sufficient.	.831				2.55	
27.The speed of service provided by the staff to the customer is sufficient.	.801				2.72	
30. The staff is friendly.	.796				2.75	
32.The company is generally of good quality.	.760				2.91	
25. The parking service of the hotel is sufficient.	.733				2.83	
23.Is it easy to get to the hotel?	.726				2.83	
24. I can quickly get information about products and services.	.726				2.92	
31.My requests are understood and answered.	.709				2.81	

The Table 3 shows that Factor analysis of customer satisfaction by using the Kaiser-MeyerOlkin (KMO) analysis was found to be 0.855; since this value is over 0.4 or even 0.5, it is shown that sampling is sufficient and meaningful factors can be obtained from research data. The fact that all expressions have a factor load more significant than 0.5 and an eigenvalue

greater than 1 indicates that the faces are suitable for analysis. Cronbach's alpha coefficient was 0.928. since this value is more significant than 0.80, the scale is highly reliable, and the variance explanation rate is 65.72%. Thus, it decided that the scale could be used scientific research only.

Table 4. Analysis of Correlations

		Employee satisfaction	Business performance	Customer satisfaction
Employee satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1	.866**	.916**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	280	280	280
Business performance	Pearson Correlation	.866**	1	.851**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	280	280	280
Customer satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.916**	.851**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	280	280	280

A statistically significant and positive relationship was found between the two variables. There was a correlation between customer satisfaction and employee satisfaction at 0.916**, a statistically significant and positive relationship. Customer satisfaction and employee satisfaction are a statistically significant relationship between the likelihood and tendency and a correlation between customer satisfaction and business performance.

Was found 0.851**, In this case, there is a statistically significant relationship

between customer satisfaction and business performance statistically significant and positive relationship was found between the variables of the relationship between employee satisfaction and business performance 0.866** (Küçük 2016). In this instance, there is a statistically significant relationship between employee satisfaction and business performance.

5. Conclusion

This study aimed to investigate the correlation between employee satisfaction,

customer satisfaction, and business performance. Theoretical and managerial implications: This current study's contribution is to relate the employee satisfaction, customer satisfaction, and business performance link to comprehensive models – employee models and customer models – which were proved in previous research. In particular, using dyadic data, this study found out employees' job satisfaction leads to customer satisfaction but not vice versa. Employee satisfaction and customer satisfaction may have different antecedent variables. Therefore, hotel establishments must demonstrate an interest in employees' welfare to enhance their sense of belonging and strengthen their commitment. Customer satisfaction may be determined depending on interaction with employees and emotional bonding or connection during the exchange, whereas employee satisfaction seems to be less affected by customer satisfaction. These findings could be interpreted that satisfied employees with high self-efficacy or cooperative orientation might be more inclined to share these emotions with customers. The results showed that the strongest correlations were between customer satisfaction, business performance, and employee satisfaction. Through this study, the researcher emphasizes the strong relationship between the three factors.

6. Discussion and Suggestions

This study's main purpose was to investigate the relationship between employee satisfaction, customer satisfaction, and business performance and improve customer satisfaction in Libyan hotels. In the study, the Pearson Correlation Analysis using SPSS software revealed a relationship between employee satisfaction. Customer satisfaction statistically significant and positive relationship was found, which represented

in the study by H1. as a whole, the findings of this study underscore the importance of understanding the role employee satisfaction plays as a resource in customer satisfaction in the Libyan hotels, these results confirm and agree with some international studies such as (Sageer, Rafat et al. 2012). This study evaluated the correlation between business performance and customer satisfaction in Libyan hotels.

In addition to Pearson Correlation Analysis has been done. The result shows a statistically significant and positive relationship between business performance and customer satisfaction, represented in research by H2. these results confirm and agree with some international studies like Kristensen, Martensen et al. (2000). and Williams and Naumann (2011). The relationship between employee satisfaction and business performance was examined by Pearson Correlation Analysis using SPSS software, which represented in research by H3—finding a statistically significant and positive relationship between these two variables. After reviewing and evaluating the research sample's answers, confirm and agree with some international studies such as Frost (2016) and (Oldham, Hackman et al. 1976).

This study, however, has some limitations. The study was conducted on the four and five-star hotels in Libya inside Tripoli due to the country's conditions. Several results can be revealed if the survey includes everyone The remaining hotel categories in Libya. The study focused on a small number of essential variables that affect the effectiveness of customer satisfaction. More reviews can use more variables that may correlate with customer satisfaction.

7. References

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